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**THE METHOD OF FINITE ELEMENTS DETERMINING THE PRESSURE
OF THE SOIL ON THE PIPE.**

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Annotation: Questions of the determination of the pressure of the soil are considered in this work on the pipe of the cylindrical profile. The Problem is decided by the method of final elements.

Key words: pressure, soil, pipe, final element, basement, cylinder

When determining the soil pressure on pipes, it is necessary to take into account such factors as: the number of threads, the relief of the embankment, the condition for supporting the pipes and other factors encountered in design practice.

Various factors encountered in design practice can be taken into account using numerical methods. Recently, in solving various kinds of applied problems, the finite element method (FEM) has been widely used. A number of works are known [1, 2], in which the FEM is successfully used to determine the soil pressure on a single laid long pipe, under various conditions of its support, taking into account the heterogeneity of the soil that composes the body of an embankment of constant height (plane deformation).

As a computational model, by analogy with works [1, 2], a weighty elastic medium containing holes and other inclusions reinforced by circular cylinders (foundation, soil inhomogeneities, etc.) is taken. In this case, for pipes, we assume that the cylinder is welded to the medium (there is no soil slippage along the pipe surface).

The partitioning of the selected computational domain is carried out in the form of tetrahedral finite elements. In this case, the grid should be denser as it approaches the pipes, because it is around the pipes that the greatest concentration of soil pressure occurs. To assess the convergence of the obtained approximate solution corresponding to a given breakdown to the exact solution, it is necessary to make a finer breakdown of the computational domain. Then a comparison should be made of the solutions corresponding to both breakdowns.

If they differ from each other by a value greater than the predetermined accuracy of calculations, then it is necessary to make an even finer third partition of the area and compare the solution corresponding to it with the solution for the second partition, e t.c.

It should be noted that with a dense arrangement of pipes in the places of their contact, "singular points" arise, in a small vicinity of which it is impossible to achieve

the necessary accuracy of calculations for any of the smallest breakdowns (at these points the theory of elasticity is inapplicable). The same points arise in the places where pipes rest on a flat base. When determining the soil pressure on rigid round pipes, which are, in particular, reinforced concrete pipes [1,2], this difficulty is easily overcome by the following method: using the FEM, the vertical and horizontal soil pressure is determined at all points of the pipe, except for a special one; at the singular point, a concentrated force is applied, directed vertically at the point support of pipes or horizontally at the point of their contact, equal in size to the area of the diagram, respectively, of the vertical and horizontal pressure of the soil acting on the pipes. The own weight of the soil of the embankment is distributed according to [1,2] over the nodes of the breakdown as follows: at each node of a given triangular finite element, we apply a concentrated downward force equal to the weight of the part of the soil bounded by this element, divided by the number of nodes. The surface load is distributed over the nodes of the upper boundary in the form of concentrated forces. If it is necessary to obtain the influence matrices (Green's function), then it is necessary to carry out calculations for a unit concentrated force, applying it sequentially at each node of the upper boundary. Modeling of materials of soil, pipes and other inclusions is carried out using the corresponding values of elastic constants (E , ν) and specific gravity. This makes it possible to take into account the conditions for supporting pipes, heterogeneity and multilayer soil of the embankment and foundation, and the multi-threading of the laying.

The division of the area into finite elements is carried out automatically under the program, which first selects points on the contour of each pipe and on the outer contour of the multi-connected area (the choice of points can also be carried out by the designer), and then draw vertical and horizontal lines through them. Thus, we get a grid of division of the area into parallelepipeds. Further, all parallelepipeds are divided by diagonals into tetrahedrons. The selection of points on the boundaries of the area is done in such a way that the alignment grid becomes denser as it approaches the pipes. The subroutine then numbers the grid nodes and finite elements, and calculates the global coordinates of the nodes. The subroutine is applicable only if the soil of the embankment is assumed to be isotropic. Taking into account more complex engineering and geological conditions, this subroutine is disabled using a special indicator. Based on the numerical results, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The maximum static soil pressure (σ_{\max}) on pipes laid in several lines at a clear distance $d = 3.0D$ from each other is less than on a single pipe by an average of 10% for the outer pipe and by 20% for the middle one. ... In this case, the value of σ_{\max} increases with increasing parameter d , having a minimum at $d = 0$ (pipes laid

close to each other) and a maximum at $d = 3,0D$, which coincides with the corresponding value for a single pipe.

2. The pressure σ_{\max} decreases with increasing Poisson's ratio ν of the soil. The largest value of the σ_{\max} value corresponds to the support on the foundation, the smallest - to the profiled base with a large angle of coverage. The pressure σ_{\max} on the outermost pipe and on the middle pipe is practically independent of the number of threads.

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